

Sensitivity analysis of major replacement rates and costs for floating wind farms

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ABSTRACT: Operation and maintenance is crucial for reducing the levelised cost of energy of floating offshore wind farms. With turbines increasing in size and being located further offshore in harsher conditions, replacing major components becomes more complex. There is also significant uncertainty in the rates and costs of major replacements. This paper presents a comprehensive sensitivity analysis of these factors. A novel semi-dynamic operation and maintenance-aware techno-economic model is introduced, using multiphase Markov models to characterise the operational lifespan of a wind farm. The analysis reveals that the levelised cost of energy in Portugal is approximately 124 €/MWh, with operating expenditures accounting for 14.37% of the levelised cost of energy. However, varying failure rates and costs can increase the levelised cost of energy to 141.88 €/MWh, with operating expenses rising to 25%.

1 INTRODUCTION

To fulfil global net zero targets, a rapid expansion of offshore wind capacity is imperative. According to the latest report from the Global Wind Energy Council, an estimated additional 380 GW of offshore wind capacity is projected within the next decade (Global Wind Energy Council 2023). Currently, most of the offshore wind power is derived from bottom-fixed offshore wind (BFOW) turbines. However, BFOW turbines are not suitable for depths greater than 60 metres, where the most powerful and consistent wind resources are located (Díaz & Guedes Soares 2022). These deep waters and wind resources can be effectively harnessed with floating offshore wind (FOW) turbines.

The commercialisation of FOW with gigawatt-scale farms is anticipated in the 2030s (Centeno-Telleria et al. 2024). However, reducing the costs of FOW technology is a prerequisite for

its widespread adoption (Centeno-Telleria et al. 2024). In addition to technological advances in floating turbines, improving port infrastructure (Crowle & Thies 2022), electrical grid capabilities (Ali et al. 2021), and optimisation of operation and maintenance (O&M) procedures (Li et al. 2023) are critical for the commercialisation of such large FOW. In fact, O&M can constitute between 20-30% of the final levelised cost of energy (*LCoE*) of FOW farms, making it a crucial area of cost reduction (McMorland et al. 2022).

Operating in deep-offshore locations with powerful and consistent wind resources allows for larger FOW turbines, potentially boosting energy production. However, these conditions also pose challenges for the O&M of FOW turbines, specially regarding major component replacements, such as blades, the gearbox and the generator (Jenkins et al. 2022). The main challenges related to major component replacements of FOW farms are:

- Greater distances from the shore gener-

ally result in harsher metocean conditions and longer travel times, reducing farm accessibility and increasing turbine downtime (Centeno-Telleria et al. 2023a).

- The jack-up vessels employed for replacing major components in BFOW turbines cannot operate in deep waters, creating a lack of technology for *on-site* heavy maintenance in deep waters.
- The growing size of wind turbines leads to heavier and more elevated components, which in turn, increases the complexity of lifting tasks (Jenkins et al. 2022).

Hence, there are relevant sources of uncertainty associated with the rates and costs of replacing major components in FOW turbines (Jenkins et al. 2022, Jenkins et al. 2022). Accordingly, analysing a wide range of replacement rates and costs and their potential impact on operational expenditure (*OpEx*) and *LCoE* is crucial for the development of FOW. However, these extensive sensitivity assessments require techno-economic models with (i) a comprehensive consideration of the O&M phase and (ii) computational efficiency.

In addition, the rates and costs associated with major replacements can vary during the operational lifetime of the FOW farm. Various factors contribute to this variance, including the maturity of the FOW industry, and the expertise acquired by manufacturers and O&M specialists. Consequently, the development of semi-dynamic techno-economic models capable of integrating these varying rates and costs throughout the analysis period becomes essential. However, it is crucial that such dynamism varying rates and costs is articulated preserving the O&M awareness and computational efficiency mentioned earlier.

This paper presents such a semi-dynamic O&M-aware techno-economic tool and a preliminary sensitivity analysis. The remainder of the paper is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the original techno-economic model and its adaptation to a semi-dynamic framework, Section 3 introduces the case study, Section 4 presents the results and discussion, and Section 5 draws the main conclusions.

2 O&M-AWARE TECHNO-ECONOMIC MODEL

The O&M-aware techno-economic model, originally presented in (Centeno-Telleria et al. 2024) and briefly described in Section 2.1, is depicted in Figure 1. The original techno-economic model thoroughly considers O&M factors and is computationally efficient. However, it lacks the capability

to adjust rates and parameter values over the analysis period. To address this limitation, the model is enhanced by incorporating multi-phase Markov models (Rausand & Hoyland 2003), thus enabling a semi-dynamic framework, as detailed in Section 2.2.

2.1 Original Techno-Economic Model

The main key performance indicator (KPI) computed through the O&M-aware techno-economic model is the *LCoE*, which is defined as follows (Centeno-Telleria et al. 2024),

$$LCoE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^T [CapEx + OpEx_i] \cdot (1+r)^{-i}}{\sum_{i=1}^T AEP_i \cdot (1+r)^{-i}}, \quad (1)$$

where r is the discount rate defined over the range $[0,1]$, AEP_i the farm-level annual energy production for the year i [MWh], $OpEx_i$ the farm-level *OpEx* for the year i [€] and T the project operational lifetime [years].

The *CapEx* [€] is computed in the pre-operational phase model as follows,

$$CapEx = C_{D\&C} + C_{turb} + C_{mooring} + C_{transmission} + C_{installation} + C_{decommission}. \quad (2)$$

where $C_{D\&C}$ is the development and consenting cost, C_{turb} the cost of the turbine, $C_{mooring}$ the moorings cost, $C_{transmission}$ the electricity transmission cost, $C_{installation}$ the cost of installing the FOW turbine and $C_{decommission}$ the decommissioning cost. All these costs are further detailed in (Centeno-Telleria et al. 2024).

The AEP_i and the $OpEx_i$ are computed in the computationally-efficient O&M model, which consists of accessibility, availability, energy and economic submodels, as shown in Figure 1. The interdependencies between these four submodels are defined by means of a Reliability Block Diagram (RBD) and Markov chains (Centeno-Telleria et al. 2023b). In this respect, the the energy generated in the FOW farm through the whole operational lifetime is defined as follows,

$$E_{production}(T) = n_{turb} \cdot A_{turb}(T) \cdot \int_{t_0=0}^T z(U_w(t)) dt, \quad (3)$$

where $A_{turb}(T)$ is the average availability of the FOW turbine [%], t_0 the initial time instant of the analysis period [h], $z(U_w(t))$ the power curve of the turbine, $U_w(t)$ the wind speed at time instant t and dt the continuous integration. $A_{turb}(T)$ is computed considering a series RBD configuration as,

$$A_{turb}(T) = A_{min}(T) \cdot A_{med}(T) \cdot A_{maj}(T), \quad (4)$$

Figure 1: Flowchart of the computationally-efficient O&M-aware techno-economic model.

where $A_{min}(T)$, $A_{med}(T)$ and $A_{maj}(T)$ represent the average availability value for minor, medium and major components, respectively.

Similarly, the farm level $OpEx$ is computed considering the O&M costs for minor $C_{min}(T)$, medium $C_{med}(T)$ and major components $C_{maj}(T)$ as follows,

$$OpEx(T) = n_{turb} \cdot [C_{min}(T) + C_{med}(T) + C_{maj}(T)] , \quad (5)$$

where each of these costs is computed summing up vessels, material and technicians costs, and the number of maintenance tasks (Centeno-Telleria et al. 2023b).

The function of minor, medium and major components is modelled by Markov chains consisting of three states: working (W), failed (F) and performing replacement (CM) states, as illustrated in Figure 2a. The steady state probability distributions of the Markov chains are of interest, which can be defined as follows,

$$\mathbf{P} = \{Pr(W), Pr(F), Pr(CM)\} , \quad (6)$$

where $Pr(W)$ represents the availability of a component used in Equation (4) to compute turbine availability. In this context, besides availability, the steady-state probability distributions also influence costs, such as $C_{min}(T)$, $C_{med}(T)$ and $C_{maj}(T)$.

In this respect, minor, medium and major components have their own \mathbf{P} , which at time T can be defined as follows,

$$\mathbf{P}(T) = \mathbf{P}(t_0) \cdot e^{\mathbf{Q} \cdot T} , \quad (7)$$

being $\mathbf{P}(t_0)$ the initial state probabilities of the Markov chain defined as $\{1, 0, 0\}$ and \mathbf{Q} the transition rate matrix. The general form of the transition

rate matrix is,

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_j & 0 & -\lambda_j \\ -\omega_j & \omega_j & 0 \\ 0 & -\mu_j & \mu_j \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where λ_j is the failure rate or the replacement rate of the component, ω_j the waiting rate given the accessibility of the farm, and μ_j the replacement duration rate of the component (Centeno-Telleria et al. 2023b).

To compute the $LCoE$ in Equation (1), it is necessary to calculate the AEP_i and $OpEx_i$ for each year i of the lifetime T . In the original techno-economic model, both the AEP_i and $OpEx_i$ are determined by assuming identical values across all operational years, averaging the total values as follows,

$$AEP_i = \frac{E_{production}(T)}{T} , \quad (9)$$

$$OpEx_i = \frac{OpEx(T)}{T} . \quad (10)$$

However, considering identical AEP and $OpEx$ for all operational years can be seen as a limitation of the model. The U_w and H_s vary each year, impacting accessibility, availability and, thus, AEP and $OpEx$. This limitation can be relaxed by a semi-dynamic techno-economic model based on multi-phase Markov models.

2.2 Semi-dynamic Techno-Economic Model

The semi-dynamic techno-economic model consists of a pre-operational phase model and a computationally-efficient O&M model. The pre-operational phase model remains the same as in the original techno-economic model. Conversely, the computationally-efficient O&M model

Figure 2: Techno-economic model with: (a) Original framework, (b) Semi-dynamic framework with multiphase Markov models.

is adapted with multiphase Markov models to establish a semi-dynamic framework.

In a multiphase Markov model, the system under consideration can be divided into multiple phases or stages, each with its own set of states and transition probabilities. In this study, each year of the operational lifetime represents a phase. The considered states of the Markov chains are identical for all phases, while the transition rate matrix \mathbb{Q}_i varies along the lifetime, as illustrated in Figure 2b.

In this sense, the process evolves with transition rate matrix \mathbb{Q}_1 until first year (t_1). Accordingly, the probability distribution after the first year can be defined as (Rausand & Hoyland 2003),

$$\mathbf{P}(t_1) = \mathbf{P}(t_0) \cdot e^{\mathbb{Q}_1 \cdot (t_1 - t_0)}. \quad (11)$$

Between t_1 and second year (t_2), the process evolves with transition matrix \mathbb{Q}_2 with the initial distribution being $\mathbf{P}(t_1)$ as follows (Rausand & Hoyland 2003),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}(t_2) &= \mathbf{P}(t_1) \cdot e^{\mathbb{Q}_2 \cdot (t_2 - t_1)} \\ &= \mathbf{P}(t_0) \cdot e^{\mathbb{Q}_1 \cdot (t_1 - t_0)} \cdot e^{\mathbb{Q}_2 \cdot (t_2 - t_1)}. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Therefore, for any year t_i , such that $1 \leq i \leq T$, the probability distribution can be computed as (Rausand & Hoyland 2003),

$$\mathbf{P}(t_i) = \mathbf{P}(t_0) \cdot \prod_{k=1}^{k=i} e^{\mathbb{Q}_k \cdot (t_k - t_{k-1})}. \quad (13)$$

As the probability distribution for each year varies, the total $AEP(T)$ and $OpEx(T)$ for the semi-dynamic techno-economic model are re-

defined in Equations (14) and (15).

$$\begin{aligned} AEP(T) &= \sum_{i=1}^T AEP_i \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^T n_{turb} \cdot A_{turb}(t_i) \cdot \int_{t_{i-1}}^{t_i} z(U_w(t)) dt. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} OpEx(T) &= \sum_{i=1}^T OpEx_i \\ &= n_{turb} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^T [C_{min}(t_i) + C_{med}(t_i) + C_{maj}(t_i)]. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

By dividing the analysis into phases and permitting the adjustment of transition rates, it is also feasible to redefine model inputs throughout the analysis, such as the O&M-related costs.

3 CASE STUDY

This section defines the case study to which the semi-dynamic techno-economic model is applied. To that end, the deployment site, the FOW technology and details regarding maintenance vessels are defined.

The techno-economic assessment is performed in Portugal in the area illustrated with a yellow box in Figure 3. One hundred semi submersible FOW turbines, each with a capacity of 10 MW and four mooring lines, are considered in that area, resulting in a total installed capacity of 1 GW. The power curve of the turbine is based on the DTU 10

MW wind turbine (Bak et al. 2013). The electricity transmission rely on high-voltage alternating current cable as the distance to shore is set at 50 km (Martinez & Iglesias 2022).

Figure 3: The yearly mean values of: (a) H_s [m], (b) U_w [m/s], and (c) Water depth [m].

The water depth for the studied area is 143 metres, which is computed from ETOPO Global Relief Model of the NOAA database at one arc-minute resolution (Amante & Eakins 2009). The operational lifespan of the FOW farms is set at 20 years ($T = 20$) with a 10% discount rate ($r = 10\%$), as defined in (Martinez & Iglesias 2022). Significant wave height (H_s) and wind speed (U_w) time-series data at a 100-metre height are obtained from the ERA5 reanalysis products provided by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (Hersbach et al. 2020). Precisely, the mean values of H_s and U_w in the studied area are 2.18 metres and 7.93 metres per second, respectively.

The turbine failure model inputs, *i.e.* replacement and costs, are described in Table 1 based on (Centeno-Telleria et al. 2024, Dinwoodie 2014). Each failure category has its own maintenance requirements. In this respect, the characteristics of maintenance vessels are defined in Table 2 based on (Centeno-Telleria et al. 2024, Li et al. 2023). In this respect, it is assumed that the HL

has the capability to perform onsite replacement, which aligns with the planned approach for future commercial-scale FOW projects (Centeno-Telleria et al. 2024). Furthermore, a technician's daily rate of 250€ is assumed (Centeno-Telleria et al. 2024).

Table 1: Characteristics for the baseline case study.

	Minor	Medium	Major
Replacement:			
- rate λ [$\frac{repl./year}{turbine}$]	1.8	0.4	0.1*
- duration rate μ [h^{-1}]	8	20	60
- cost [k€]	2.8	5.6	2400*
Vessel	CTV	SOV	HLV

*: A sensitivity assessment of these parameters is performed in this paper.

Table 2: Characteristics of selected maintenance vessels.

	CTV	SOV	HLV
Vessel speed [knots]	24	10	12.5
H_s limit [m]	1.5	2	1.5
U_w limit [m/s]	30	30	10
Day rate [k€/day]	1.98	10.8	409
Mobilisation cost [k€]	1.14	2.84	2045
Fuel consumption [mt/h]	0.24	0.2	0.55
Fuel cost [€/mt]	300	300	450
Required technicians	2	4	6

4 RESULTS

This section presents and discusses the main results of this paper. Firstly, the differences in KPIs between the original and semi-dynamic techno-economic models are evaluated. Then, a sensitivity assessment on major replacement rates and costs is performed based on the semi-dynamic techno-economic model.

The yearly mean values for availability, AEP and $OpEx$ with both the original and semi-dynamic models are computed and presented in Figure 4. The mean availability, AEP and $OpEx$ with the original techno-economic model are 98.27%, 3744 GWh, and 56.8 m€, respectively. In contrast, computed via the semi-dynamic techno-economic model, availability can range from 97.55% to 98.66%, AEP from 3235 GWh to 4327 GWh and $OpEx$ from 56.61 m€ to 57.04 m€. These differences in yearly KPIs have a direct impact on the final $LCoE$ of the FOW farm, which varies from 118.37 €/MWh with the original techno-economic model to 118.77 €/MWh with the semi-dynamic model. Additionally, the original techno-economic model requires, on average, 0.85 seconds to compute those KPIs, whereas the semi-dynamic techno-economic model requires

1.76 seconds. Despite a slight increase in computational time, the new semi-dynamic techno-economic model remains computationally very efficient.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4: The KPIs obtained with the original and enhanced semi-dynamic techno-economic model: (a) Availability [%], (b) AEP [GWh], and (c) OpEx [m€].

However, although the transition rate λ that defines the major replacements per year has been kept constant during the phases in Figure 4, the semi-dynamic framework enables the variation of all transition rates among phases. In this respect, a sensitivity assessment of λ is performed following a commonly used bathtub curve, which defines the occurrences of major replacements over years,

as shown in Figure 5. Three typical intervals are commonly defined in a bathtub curve: the infant mortality period, the useful life period, and the wear-out period (Rausand & Hoyland 2003). The infant mortality period highlights higher likelihood of failures occurring shortly after deployment due to manufacturing defects or early stress. Following the infant mortality phase, the useful life period represents the stable phase where the system operates at a relatively constant rate. Finally, in the wear-out period, the system experiences an increasing failure rate as it approaches the end of its operational life due to ageing.

Figure 5: The considered bathtub curves for major replacements over years in the semi-dynamic techno-economic model. In the original techno-economic model the replacement rate is considered constant over the whole operational lifetime.

The sensitivity of $LCoE$ as a function of λ and the cost per replacement is depicted in Figure 6. The $LCoE$ with the baseline bathtub curve using the semi-dynamic model is 123.96 €/MWh, where the $OpEx$ represents 14.37% of the $LCoE$. In this respect, the $LCoE$ with the baseline bathtub curve using the semi-dynamic model is 5.59 €/MWh higher compared to the $LCoE$ value computed with the original techno-economic model baseline, where the same λ is considered long the whole lifetime. This increase in $LCoE$ with the semi-dynamic model arises from higher λ values both during the first 5 years and the last 5 years of the operational lifetime. Furthermore, Figure 6 illustrates that $LCoE$ increases with higher λ and costs. Specifically, at the highest λ and costs, the $LCoE$ value is 141.88 €/MWh (a 14.45% increase), with $OpEx$ accounting for 24.75% of the $LCoE$. In contrast, at the lowest λ and costs, the value of $LCoE$ is 110.14 €/MWh (an 11.15% decrease), with $OpEx$ representing 4.15% of the $LCoE$.

Figure 6: The sensitivity of the $LCoE$ as a function of major component replacement rate and cost.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Operation and maintenance (O&M) is a crucial area of cost reduction for floating offshore wind (FOW). As FOW turbines grow in size and operate farther offshore exposed to harsher metocean conditions, the complexity of conducting major component replacements also increases. Due to the low level of maturity, nowadays, there is considerable uncertainty about the rates and costs of major replacements for FOW turbines. This uncertainty regarding the potential impact of major replacement rates and costs can be reduced by performing extensive sensitivity assessments using techno-economic models that characterise the whole operational lifetime of a FOW farm. In this context, techno-economic models must encompass three characteristics:

- (i) Comprehensive consideration of O&M factors, such as weather windows, failures rates of components, replacement duration, maintenance vessels' operational limits and capacities, and maintenance strategies.
- (ii) Computational-efficiency given the large variability of the input O&M variables, such as replacement rates and costs.
- (iii) Dynamism in the model given the variability in the values of input O&M variables throughout the operational lifetime of a FOW farm.

In this paper a techno-economic model incorporating these three characteristics is introduced. To achieve this, the authors enhance the initial version of the techno-economic model with multiphase Markov models. Subsequently, the enhanced semi-dynamic techno-economic framework is employed to conduct an extensive sensitivity analysis of replacement rates and costs.

The results presented in this paper reveal that the levelised cost of energy ($LCoE$) in the studied area of Portugal, under a baseline scenario, is 123.96 €/MWh, with operating expenditure ($OpEx$) comprising 14.37% of $LCoE$. However, a variation of 0.1 of the replacement rate in major components results in significantly higher replacement costs, increasing the $LCoE$ up to 141.88 €/MWh and the $OpEx$ representing 24.75% of the $LCoE$.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support from the Basque Government for the Predoctoral Training Research Grant Number [PRE_2023_2.0290], Spain under Grant Number [PID2021-124245OA-I00] (MINECO/FEDER, UE), the European Union Horizon Europe programme under the agreement 101136087 (INF4INITY Project) and Basque Government's ELKARTEK 2024 program under the grant No. KK-2024/00073.

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